

An Improved Speech Enhancement with GSC Beamformer

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Abstract

Microphone array (MA) beamformer use the prior spatial information about the assumed direction of arrival of interest useful signal, the characteristics of surrounding noise field, the designed configuration of MA, the observed properties of received array signals, the capability of integrating with different signal processing algorithm for obtaining advantage in suppressing the background noise level and speech enhancement under complex and adverse situations. Generalized sidelobe canceller (GSC) beamformer is one of the most effective solutions, which has common integrated into voice-controlled devices, hearing aids, smart home, teleconference system, smart vehicle transport for removing the unwanted noise component and extracting the desired target speaker with satisfied speech quality. GSC beamformer concerns the beampattern at specified location and applies an adaptive noise canceller to take into account the clean speech data. However, because of the complexity of recorded conditions, GSC beamformer's performance often corrupted. In this article, the author introduce an efficient method for enhancing the robust of beamformer in real-life situations. The numerical simulation has confirmed the effectiveness of reducing the surrounding noise level to 12.8 dB and improve the obtained signal-to-noise ratio from 13.2 to 13.9 dB.

I. Introduction

In several human-machine interaction system, such as, smart home, surveillance devices, teleconferencing equipment, smart intelligent transport, smart phone, it is important to remove the affect of background noise, interference or annoying environment as in Figure 1.

An efficient solution is using MA beamforming [1-3] to concern the steerable beampattern at specified direction while attenuating surrounding noise field. The scheme of MA is given by Figure with perspective effectiveness of noise suppression and speech enhancement. MA utilizes the small-aperture range for achieving higher directivity index and directivity factor.

Figure 1: The complex surrounding noise around human life

GSC beamformer is an efficient solution for preserving the clean speech data while suppressing the surrounding noise field at certain locations. GSC beamformer own the low computation, low complexity and flexible ability of intergrating with different signal processing algorithms. However, due to the microphone mismatches, the difference of microphone sensitivities, the error of sampling frequency, the internal electrical noise, the displacement of microphone geometry, the presence of undetermined reasons, GSC beamformer’s evaluation usually degraded. The speech distortion or musical noise, ambient noise significantly corrupt the speech quality of output signal. There are many efforts were studied for overcoming this drawback.

Figure 2: The steerable beampattern at certain sound location

Li S et al [4] analyzed the use of variable step size least mean square method for reducing the effect of diffuse noise field. The numerical results has confirmed the advantages of increasing the robust of speech enhancement and noise reduction in real-life situations.

Park J et al [5] proposed determinant-based GSC, which contains two stages suppression techniques with Wiener filter and removing residual noise by applying determinant-based adaptation noise canceller. The demonstrated experiments were conducted in realistic recording scenario with perspective opinion score.

Kim S. M et al [6] implemented phase difference between two observed microphone signals for calculating the target-to-non-target directional signal ratio for adaptive tracking and updating the smoothing parameter in the fixed beamformer of GSC structure. The suggested technique was performed under real-life situations with promising results of perceptual quality and intelligibility score.

In [7], Wang J proposed a robust adjusting rule for adaptive interference suppression, which derived from a time-varying Gaussian distribution. The updating of coefficients is followed by maximum likelihood criterion. The simulation has shown the robustness and effectiveness of the author's suggested technique over the existing conventional methods.

Wang Q et al [8] addressed the problem of inaccurate estimation of direction of arrival of useful signal by redesigning the blocking matrix configuration with eigenanalysis for reconstructing interference-plus-noise from the samples. The blocking matrix own superiority of mitigating the speech component while passes the only noise component. The obtained numerical simulation has confirmed the ability of againsting mismatches.

Unfortunately, these mention techniques can not deal with real-life problems under complex conditions. In this contribution, the authors presented an efficient solution for resovling the problem of unacceptable musical noise, residual noise at GSC beamformer's output.

II. GSC Beamformer

The structure of GSC beamformer in the frequency-domain is illustrated in Figure 3. The author used dual-microphone system (DMA2) for describing the pricipal working of GSC beamformer for extracting the desired target speech component while mitigating the background noise field.

The assumed direction of arrival of interest signal is θ_s to the axis of DMA2. At current considered frame k , current frequency f , the formulation of received array signals $X_1(f, k)$, $X_2(f, k)$ can be expressed as:

$$X_1(f, k) = S(f, k)e^{j\phi_s} + N_1(f, k) \quad (1)$$

$$X_2(f, k) = S(f, k)e^{-j\phi_s} + N_2(f, k) \quad (2)$$

where the original speech data $S(f, k)$, $\Phi_s = \pi f \tau_0 \cos(\theta_s)$ is the phase delay, which describes the relation between target signal and microphones, $\tau_0 = d/c$, d is the range between microphones, $c = 343(m/s)$ is the sound speed in fresh air; additive noise, third-party talker, different types of noise, interference or annoying environment is denoted as $N_1(f, k)$, $N_2(f, k)$.

Figure 3: The illustrated model of GSC beamformer

GSC beamformer contains three parts: the fixed beamformer, which concerns the beampattern at certain location with main signal $Y_m(f, k)$; blocking matrix is applied for blockign the speech component while passes the only noise compoent as reference signal $Y_r(f, k)$, the essential core is adaptive noise canceller (ANC), which reduces background noise and obtain the desired speaker by using reference signal. ANC often uses Wiener filter.

The expression of $Y_m(f, k)$, $Y_r(f, k)$ can be calculated as the equations:

$$Y_m(f, k) = \frac{X_1(f, k)e^{-j\Phi_s} + X_2(f, k)e^{j\Phi_s}}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_r(f, k) = \frac{X_1(f, k)e^{-j\Phi_s} - X_2(f, k)e^{j\Phi_s}}{2} \quad (4)$$

The coefficients of Wiener filter can be computed as:

$$H_{Wiener}(f, k) = \frac{E\{Y_m(f, k)Y_r^*(f, k)\}}{E\{|Y_r(f, k)|^2\}} \quad (5)$$

Where the auto-cross power spectral densities (PSD) of $Y_m(f, k)$, $Y_r(f, k)$ can be recursively determined as:

$$P_{Y_m Y_r}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_m Y_r}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) Y_m(f, k) Y_r^*(f, k) \quad (6)$$

$$P_{Y_r Y_r}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_r Y_r}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) |Y_r(f, k)|^2 \quad (7)$$

with α is an appropriate smoothing parameter in the range $\{0 \dots 1\}$.

And the final signal of GSC beamformer is derived as:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{GSC}(f, k) &= Y_m(f, k) - H_{Wiener}(f, k) \times Y_r(f, k) \\ &= Y_m(f, k) - \frac{P_{Y_m Y_r}(f, k)}{P_{Y_r Y_r}(f, k)} \times Y_r(f, k) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Unfortunately, due to the complex and adverser recording situation and different undetermined reasons, the overall GSC beamformer's performance often degraded. In the next section, the author will introduce an efficient approach for reducing the musical noise and increasing speech quality.

III. The author's proposed method

The paper's idea is deriving two additive reference signal for obtaining more robust of noise reduction. The author use a priori signal-to-noise ratio $SNR(f, k)$ for forming spectral mask $\frac{1}{1+SNR(f, k)}$ to achieve supported reference signals as:

$$Y_{r1}(f, k) = \frac{1}{1 + SNR(f, k)} \times X_1(f, k) \quad (9)$$

$$Y_{r2}(f, k) = \frac{1}{1 + SNR(f, k)} \times X_2(f, k) \quad (10)$$

where the priori $SNR(f, k)$ can be calculated as [9]:

$$SNR(f, k) = \frac{1 + \cos(\Phi_{12,k}^{norm}(f))}{4(1 - \cos(\Phi_{12,k}^{norm}(f)))} \quad (11)$$

with $\Phi_{12,k}^{norm}(f) = \frac{\angle(X_1(f, k)) - \angle(X_2(f, k))}{2\pi f \tau_0}$, $\angle(X_1(f, k))$, $\angle(X_2(f, k))$ is phases of received array signals.

The expression of auto and cross PSD of $Y_{r1}(f, k)$, $Y_{r2}(f, k)$ and $Y_m(f, k)$ can be derived from the following equations:

$$P_{Y_m Y_{r1}}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_m Y_{r1}}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) Y_m(f, k) Y_{r1}^*(f, k) \quad (12)$$

$$P_{Y_m Y_{r2}}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_m Y_{r2}}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) Y_m(f, k) Y_{r2}^*(f, k) \quad (13)$$

$$P_{Y_{r1} Y_{r1}}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_{r1} Y_{r1}}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) |Y_{r1}(f, k)|^2 \quad (14)$$

$$P_{Y_{r2} Y_{r2}}(f, k) = \alpha P_{Y_{r2} Y_{r2}}(f, k - 1) + (1 - \alpha) |Y_{r2}(f, k)|^2 \quad (15)$$

With uncorrelated two additive signals $Y_{r1}(f, k)$, $Y_{r2}(f, k)$, the musical noise or ambient noise at GSC beamformer's output signal can be filtered as:

$$\hat{Y}_{GSC}(f, k) = Y_m(f, k) - \frac{P_{Y_m Y_r}(f, k)}{P_{Y_r Y_r}(f, k)} \times Y_r(f, k) - \frac{P_{Y_m Y_{r1}}(f, k)}{P_{Y_{r1} Y_{r1}}(f, k)} \times Y_{r1}(f, k) - \frac{P_{Y_m Y_{r2}}(f, k)}{P_{Y_{r2} Y_{r2}}(f, k)} \times Y_{r2}(f, k) \quad (16)$$

In the next section, the author will perform an experiments for illustrating the capabilities of this approach for increasing the robust of GSC beamformer's performance under realistic recording environments.

IV. Experiments and discussion

Figure 4: The demonstrated experiment in real-life living room

The aim of this section is demonstrating the effectiveness of the author’s method in suppressing the background noise field, interference or third-party speaker. The experiment was conducted in living room (3.5x4x4.5(m)) with presence of the sound of washing machine, television, fan, air conditioner. The configuration of experiment is shown in Figure 4.

For estimating the speech quality, an objective measurement [10] is used for computing the signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio between MA signals, the processed signals by traditional GSC beamformer and presented method (premt). In addition, the information about waveform, spectrum and energy were illustrated for verifying the enhanced GSC beamformer’s evaluation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: The waveform (a) and spectrogram (b) of original microphone array signals.

A speaker, which stand at distance $L = 5(m)$ to the axis of DMA2. The distance between microphones is $d = 5(cm)$. The assumed incident angle is $\theta_s = 90(deg)$. For capturing the noisy mixture of desired speaker, the adverse background noise field, these parameters are used: frequency sampling $F_s = 16kHz$, the overlap 50%. The received array signals can be shown in Figure 5.

For processing the signal in frequency-domain, the paper used Hamming window, $nFFT = 512$ and $\alpha = 0.1$ for performing MVDR beamformer. The resulting signal can be shown in Figure 6.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: The conventional GSC beamformer's output signal: waveform (a) and spectrogram (b).

From these above figure, we can realize that, because of the microphone mismatches, the error of sampling frequency, the displacement of microphone geometry, the different microphone sensitivities, the movement of talker, which cause the imprecise estimation of steering vector, the undetermined acoustic event and different factors, the overall GSC beamformer's output signal is not satisfied the perceptual metric listener. The amount of ambient noise, musical noise and residual noise degrade still large and reduce the speech intelligibility of beamformer's result.

Therefore, the author's suggested technique derived two additive noise reference for continuing removing background noise field. This approach allowed achieving perspective results with removing surrounding noise field and increasing the speech quality.

The overall speech enhancement's results yields as:

(a)

Figure 7: The promising signal by using premtD: waveform (a) and spectrogram (b).

Figure 8: The comparison with energy between signals

Figure 8 and Table 1 presented the curve of energy between the observed MA signals, the processed signal by GSC beamformer and premtD

Method Estimation	Microphone array signal	GSC beamformer	premtD
NIST STNR	5.8	13.5	26.7
WADA SNR	3.5	11.6	25.5

Table 1: The comparison SNR (dB)

The advantage of *premt*d is illustrated in suppressing the ambient noise field to 12.8 dB and improving the speech quality in the term of signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio in range 13.2 - 13.9 dB. With more uncorrelated reference signal, the effectiveness of noise reduction of GSC beamformer is consolidated.

From the above figure and Table 1, this article concludes some assessments as:

(1) GSC beamformer own the capability of steerable the pattern the specified location with high directivity index. The effectiveness is given by the saving the clean speech data and attenuating the adverse surrounding noise field.

(2) Because of mentioned reasons, there is still exists unacceptable noise component, which reduces the speech intelligibility and other perceptual metric listener. In our experiment, the ambient noise cause corrupted performance.

(3) By using the spatial prior information of incident angle of helpful signal, the paper obtained two additive reference signal, $Y_{r1}(f, k)$, $Y_{r2}(f, k)$, which is not correlated with $Y_r(f, k)$. The ANC part of GSC beamformer performs by using reference signal to eliminate the noise component at main signal. As a result, more additive reference signal will promote ANC part suppressed surrounding noise component and preserving the target speech.

(4) The appealing properties of *premt*d is removing ambient noise field while does not distorting speech. This method has low computation and very suitable for different acoustic equipments to address more complicated problems.

V. Conclusion

Speech enhancement is an essential core in numerous speech applications with purpose of saving the target talker and attenuating the interference, surrounding noise field or third-party speaker at different directions with high speech quality. GSC beamformer works well in stationary noise field with perspective performance in extracting the desired target speaker while suppressing background noise field. In this contribution, the author suggested using the prior information about impinging angle of useful signal for achieving an efficient spectral mask, which used for deriving two additive noise reference signal. The advantage of this technique is utilizing more reference signal for reducing unacceptable musical noise field, ambient noise field to 12.8 dB and increasing the signal-to-noise ratio from 13.2 to 13.9 dB. The author's suggested technique can address other complicated problems, dereverberation, speech acquisition, speech recognition.

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